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ABSTRACTS

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Modelling and analysis of multi-analyte based microfluidics system

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Abstract: The modern healthcare sector has been revolutionized by the advent of point-of-care (POC) devices which enable rapid, accurate, and non-invasive diagnosis of patients around the world through their integration into wearable devices. The presence of microlevel POCs in wearable systems can enable continuous and precise monitoring of various diseases which leave behind distinct, detectable biomarkers in the form of biofluids. Microfluidics allow for the sensing of changes in the properties of fluids, and offer feasible methods for their control. In this research project, we aim to design a multi-layered microfluidic system that analyzes multiple clinical markers including, but not limited to, glucose, lactate, urea, and pH in order to facilitate the early diagnosis of hyperosmolar hyperglycemic state (HHS), a complex condition of diabetes. This design will be implemented on the user-friendly platform, COMSOL Multiphysics, utilizing its features to explore different microchannel geometries, optimize fluid flow rates, and predict the behavior of different analytes.

Keywords: Point of care devices, wearable devices, microfluidics, hyperosmolar hyperglycemic state, sweat, clinical markers, glucose, lactate, urea, pH, COMSOL Multiphysics.

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